

Developing Effectivity of Student's Speaking Skill through Questions and Answers Method at Elementary School

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Abstract

The utilization of the question and answer method fosters instructor engagement with students, aligning with the self-directed curriculum. This study assesses learning outcomes across all domains, specifically cognitive, emotional, and psychomotor. The research findings indicate a rise in every domain with each cycle. Through this experimental methodology, pupils acquire the understanding that they possess the capacity to learn effectively. Using this approach, researchers develop engaging and age-appropriate instructional sessions. The utilization of the question and response method in enhancing students' speaking skills is expected to foster cognitive function, enabling pupils to think proficiently and swiftly.

Keywords: Speaking Skill, Q and A Method, SDN Karang Nangkah I

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Introduction

English is a globally spoken foreign language (Noviana & Oktaviani, 2022). English is the second language in Indonesia (Lowenberg, 1991). As human beings, it is necessary for us to acquire knowledge, either through structured education or through informal means (Scribner & Cole, 1973). Learning is an individual's cognitive process of acquiring knowledge or understanding about a certain subject or concept (Zein et al., 2020). Education is a crucial aspect in the globe (Maghsudi et al., 2021).

Learning is the process of modifying one's behavior through the acquisition of knowledge and the application of practice (Reisoğlu & Çebi, 2020). It refers to a modification in behavior, encompassing knowledge, skills, attitudes, and all characteristics of the individual or organism (Ryder, 1985). The method of instruction employed by researchers is based on a question and response format. The questions and answers here encourage pupils to engage in verbal communication. The researcher anticipates that employing this question and response methodology will enhance pupils' reading proficiency.

Given the limited technological resources available in the schools selected for the study, the researchers utilized guidebooks, markers, and blackboards as instructional tools. The researcher selected SDN Karang Nangkah due to its proximity to their location. SDN Karang Nangkah 1 is situated in the Blega region within Karang Nangkah village, which falls under the same sub-district as the researcher. This school has rather satisfactory accessibility in comparison to other isolated regions. The place is conveniently accessible via the Blega main road, however if approached from the researcher's residence, entrance to it is characterized by a significant incline.

SDN Karang Nangkah 1 consists of 6 classrooms and 1 building designated as the teacher's office. The lower level is designated for students in grades 1, 2, 3, and 4. On the second floor, grades 5 and 6 are accommodated. Additionally, researchers classify an object as class 5. He was victorious in an MTQ competition among sub-districts at SDN Karang Nangkah 1, serving as a catalyst for motivating fellow students to engage in healthy competition and strive for excellence.

A relevance study is considered by researchers to be almost identical to their own research. The first research entitled, "The implementation of fun fishing to teach speaking for elementary school students" was compiled by (Sinaga & Oktaviani, 2020). This research, the researchers want to see the use of Fun Fishing in teaching speaking at one of the Elementary Schools in Lampung to encourage students in learning English. This research used a qualitative method since it disclosed how to implement Fun Fishing media in an Elementary School in Lampung. As a result, the students were divided into four groups consisted of 2-3 members and learned English which involved physical activity. To sum up, using this media in learning English can motivate students to speak in English and make teaching and learning become more fun because they did physical activity.

Second, research entitled, "Enhancing students' speaking skills with language games" was arranged by (Nazarov, 2023). The article considers the possibilities of using speaking games in the process of teaching a foreign language at a university. The main classifications of games are given, while the main attention is paid to games of a lexical nature. The article substantiates the conditions that allow the most effective use of speaking games in foreign language classes, and also provides examples of games at different stages of working with students. Examples of games in a foreign language lesson with different stages of work with students are given to enhance students' speaking skills.

Third, research entitled, "The effectiveness of partial pair programming on elementary school students' Computational Thinking skills and self-efficacy" was compiled by (Wei et

al., 2021). The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of partial pair programming (PPP) on elementary school students' CT skills and self-efficacy (SE). The study included four 4th grade classes, with a total of 171 students, who were taking the course entitled "Computational Thinking with Scratch" with the same teacher for one semester. Two classes (84 students) were in the Experimental Group (EG, 44 boys and 40 girls) while two other classes (87 students) were in the Control Group (CG, 45 boys and 42 girls). The students in the EG were paired up for the programming assignments while the students in the CG did the assignments on their own. The results showed that the students in the EG improved their CT skills and SE more significantly than those in the CG group. There was a low correlation between CT and SE in the post-test of both groups. The interviews with the teacher and the students afterwards provided insights in understanding the results. The findings suggest that in K-12 programming teachers could use PPP as an effective approach to improve students' CT skills, programming SE, and beyond.

Fourth, research entitled, "The use of small-group discussion to improve students speaking skill" was arranged by (Crisianita & Mandasari, 2022). This research aimed at identifying student's improvement on their speaking mastery after learning using small group discussion in the classroom. The participant of this study is students of senior high school in Lampung province. Data gathered through questionnaire. The result of this research that using small group discussion in improving speaking skill to be effective, because in small group students more confidence to deliver their idea and criticize to think and matches the characteristics of children as a learner.

Finally, research entitled, "The impact of cooperative learning on developing speaking ability and motivation Toward learning English" was arranged by (Ehsan et al., 2019). This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of cooperative learning in English language classrooms to enhance Iranian students' speaking skills and motivations. A pre-test-post-test control group design was employed to compare the impact of the cooperative learning approach with that of traditional whole-class instruction on speaking skills and six aspects of learning motivation: intrinsic motivation, integrated regulation, identified regulation, interjected regulation, external regulation, and a motivation. The data of the current study were gathered at multiple points of time before and after the end of the experiment to determine the effectiveness of cooperative learning on the sample's speaking skills and motivations. In practical terms, the sample's speaking skills were first examined through an English oral test prior to and after some cooperative learning instructional activities were provided. Next, a seven-point Likert scale-questionnaire was administered to

the sample before and at the end of the course to check students' motivation towards the use of cooperative learning in English classes. The data were analyzed using basic and inferential statistical methods including mean scores, standard deviations, independent and paired sample t-tests, one-way ANCOVA, and effect size. The findings showed remarkable development in the students' speaking skills after the introduction of cooperative learning techniques. Moreover, the findings suggested significant differences in favor of cooperative learning for improving intrinsic motivation, but no differences were found on other aspects of motivation. In light of the findings, the researchers recommend that teachers could benefit from applying CL in English classes, which may in turn develop students' speaking skills and motivation.

A few researchers focused on how to develop the student's speaking through Q and A method effectively. There have been limited studies concerned on models of techniques in learning English, such as cooperative learning, small-group discussion, partial pair programming, games, and fun fishing. Therefore, this research intends to see the development of student's speaking skill when they learn through Q and A method. The objectives of this research are increasing the student's vocabulary, introducing and preserve to students the Q and A method, and make children more creative in developing their speaking skill using Q and A method.

Research Method

The researcher took a qualitative-descriptive method. Qualitative methods are methods that focus on in-depth observations (Roller, 2019). Hence, the utilization of qualitative methodologies in research can yield a more exhaustive examination of a situation (Kaplan & Maxwell, 2005). Qualitative research methods is a research method based on the philosophy of postpositivism, used to examine the condition of natural objects (Maoula et al., 2022), (as the opposite is the experiment) where the researcher is the instrument key, data collection techniques are carried out in triangulation (combined), data analysis is inductive/qualitative in nature (Cooper et al., 2012), and the results of qualitative research are more emphasize the meaning of generalizations.

Data collection is the process of collecting, measuring, and analyzing types of information using standards (Sileyew, 2019). Data collection is searching, recording, and collecting everything objectively and as is in accordance with the results of observations and interviews in the field, namely data recording and various forms of data in the field (Baumel et al., 2019).

Observation

Observation is a very important form of data collection (Puspitarini & Hanif, 2019). In addition, observation is a very useful systematic and hidden way to observe and listen to interactions or phenomena that occur (Lofland et al., 2022). Observation can be said to be the basis of all science (Norris, 1985). In this study the researcher directly observed grade 5 for one week to assess students' English skills.

Interview

Interview is a form of method in seeking information (Pandey & Pandey, 2021). Interviews can be very flexible or free when the interviewer has the freedom to arrange the questions that are in his mind about the problem to be solved (Witzel & Reiter, 2012). However, on the other hand, the interviewer cannot be flexible if the researcher must precisely keep all the questions that have been set in writing (Kleinsasser, 2000). In this case the researcher conducted interviews directly with the principal of SDN KarangNangkah 1 to obtain information related to students English learning abilities.

Documentation

Documentation is a record of events that have passed (Sjöberg et al., 2021). Documentation can be in the form of written pictures or someone's monumental work (Graham, 2021). The documentation is used to collect data from sources that can strengthen the research process. The documentation technique is used in passive data collection (Perdisci et al., 2020), namely recording events that have passed, either in the form of written pictures or someone's monumental works. In this case the researcher took documentation relating to the results of research in the field.

Technique of Analysis

Data analysis is to find useful information and inform a conclusion (Raji et al., 2020). Data analysis techniques are analytical activities in research by examining all data various research instruments, such as notes, documents, test results, recordings, and so on (Mezmir, 2020). So, this activity makes the data easier for us to understand so we can draw a conclusion. Qualitative data analysis is an effort made by working with data (O'Kane et al., 2021), organizing data, sorting it into a single data unit that is managed, synthesizing, searching and finding patterns, finding what is important and what is learned and deciding what can be told. to others.

Result and Discussion

From the results of research conducted at SDN Karang Nangkah 1, there were 35 students who took part in the implementation of the implementation of English day to improve their English skills. The results showed that 75% of Grade 5 students at SDN Karang Nangkah 1 said they really liked this program. This means that 20 students really like the implementation of English day in learning English and 5 students don't like it. Meanwhile, 10 students did not really like (moderately) the implementation of English skill by question and answer. The students' speaking ability before implementing English day by question and answer was still at a humble level. Based on the results of the initial test, the accumulation of assessment aspects which include pronunciation and vocabulary, shows that students' speaking abilities are in the range of an average score of 20 which still includes less. Whereas after the implementation of English Day the students' English speaking ability experienced a significant increase of 40, which means there was an increase of 20.

Of the 35 students who took part in learning English with the implementation of question and answer, there were 5 students who did not like learning English using the implementation of English day.

Based on the results of the study, the results of the implementation of question and answer in improving English language skills at SDN Karang Nangkah 1, were obtained. can be presented as follows:

NO	Students Name	Students Response			Response
		Accept	Currently	Don't Accept	
1	Rahmatullah Raihan	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.

2	Ach. Fauziabdillah		✓	Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
3	Jalaluddin		✓	From some students there were those who could not accept it, it could be said that the student respondents also had a negative attitude towards learning English. This means that there are students who lack confidence in learning English, because the vocabulary is very minimal.
4	Moh. Irfan		✓	Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This

					means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
5	M. Azkazaidnir		✓		The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
6	Nengzeh			✓	From some students there were those who could not accept it, it could be said that the student respondents also had a negative attitude towards learning English. This means that there are students who lack confidence

					in learning English, because the vocabulary is very minimal.
7	Nurhanifah		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
8	Muslahuddin Latif		✓		The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
9	Ahmad Fuadi			✓	From some students there were those who could not accept it, it could be said that the student respondents

					also had a negative attitude towards learning English. This means that there are students who lack confidence in learning English, because the vocabulary is very minimal.
10	Arinimirzahilyana			✓	The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
11	As'adularobi			✓	From some students there were those who could not accept it, it could be said that the student respondents also had a negative attitude towards learning English. This means that there are students who

					lack confidence in learning English, because the vocabulary is very minimal.
12	Badressholeh			✓	From some students there were those who could not accept it, it could be said that the student respondents also had a negative attitude towards learning English. This means that there are students who lack confidence in learning English, because the vocabulary is very minimal.
13	Elisa Putri Farmida			✓	The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
14	Hilyatunnisak			✓	Student responses are also not always

					good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
15	Jamaizatul Jannah	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
16	Kamila Indah Farhana	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that

					researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
17	Kamila	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah I. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
18	Lindawati		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
19	Milyatul Islamiyah	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English

					which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah I. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
20	Mohammad Andrer A		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
21	Moh. Fahri	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah I. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their

					willingness to learn is high.
22	Nailatulfadhilah	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
23	Nafisatulmamlu'ah	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
24	Nurul Fitriyana Urahilwa		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral

					level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
25	Nurul Afidah		✓		The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
26	Rizki			✓	Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.

27	Saiful	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
28	Saiful Bahri		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating in language learning, it's just that students are lacking in mastering vocabulary.
29	Sitiaisyah	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1.

					Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
30	Shofia	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah I. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
31	Ulfatun Aini	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah I. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
32	Nuria Wahyuni	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards

					learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
33	Misbahul Munir	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to learn is high.
34	Ekaramadani	✓			The response or attitude of the students was very good towards learning English which was carried out by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. Students receive every lesson that researchers provide and their willingness to

					learn is high.
35	Ahmad Fuadi		✓		Student responses are also not always good or bad in receiving English learning materials. This means that the student respondents are at a neutral level, students are confident in participating language learning.

SDN Karang Nangkah 1 is a school located in a rural area, but its strategic location is not very rural. what researchers found in the teaching and learning process of students, especially English, teachers tend to give lecture methods. from this method the interaction between the teacher and students is not intense. The school does not have an English teacher, which results in students not knowing English. due to the absence of an English teacher, the sports teacher must fill in English in certain classes.

The researcher took the question and answer method, because according to the researcher this method was very effective if applied in this school. Class that was initially not conducive, suddenly became conducive when this method was implemented. and not only that, students are also very happy with this method, and even they ask to continue to be taught by researchers.

There are also steps that the researcher took during the process of learning English with question and answer media, namely:

1. Introduction to vocabulary

The researcher will give the vocabulary first to the students.

2. Memorization

Students will be required to memorize the vocabulary or expressions

3. Frequently asked questions

In this debriefing, students after passing through the first and second stages, will be asked questions. The question and answer must be accompanied by a fun game, so that students do not feel bored with this learning

Conclusion

English language is a foreign language that is often considered difficult by some circles, especially at the student level. But learning English will be easy and fun when the method used is in accordance with the student's environment. As was done by researchers at SDN Karang Nangkah 1. All grade 5 students considered learning English difficult, and even when they heard English, they immediately expressed disapproval. They think the most difficult subject is learning English. But with this question and answer method they responded well. The researcher gave vocabulary to students, after that asked them to remember the material that had been delivered, and then asked and answered the material. 75 percent of them responded favorably.

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